

Building Interoperable Knowledge Graphs with X3ML Framework

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Outline

Introduction	4-7	5'
X3ML Framework	8-18	10'
X3ML Software	19-44	30'
Looking to the Future	45-54	7'
Conclusion	55-58	3'
Q&A Session	59	5'

Supplementary Resources

Description Learning Objectives Format and Schedule Audience Presenter Material

Building Interoperable Knowledge Graphs with X3ML Framework

Tutorial at IJCKG 2025, October 16, 2025

Description

This tutorial introduces participants to the X3ML Framework, a suite of specifications and tools for constructing knowledge graphs from structured data. The tutorial will provide both conceptual foundations and hands-on demonstrations, guiding attendees through the workflow of defining schema mappings and transforming source data into RDF aligned with domain ontologies. At the core of the framework is a declarative, technology-agnostic mapping language that supports collaborative and maintainable schema mapping practices. Participants will learn how X3ML facilitates not only the creation of semantic mappings but also the exploration and verification of the resulting knowledge graphs to ensure correctness and completeness. The session will further highlight domain-independent applications of X3ML across fields such as cultural heritage and biodiversity, while also showcasing emerging methods that integrate Large Language Models (LLMs) to accelerate and simplify schema mapping tasks.

Learning Objectives

By the end of this tutorial participants will be able to:

- understand the principles and challenges of transforming heterogeneous source data into RDF knowledge graphs
- apply the X3ML mapping language and associated tools to design, implement and validate schema mappings
- gain hands-on experience in generating semantically rich knowledge graphs and verifying their quality
- explore innovative techniques leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs) to reduce manual effort and enhance the schema mapping process

Equipped with this knowledge, participants will be able to effectively use X3ML framework in real-world scenarios to build interoperable, semantically robust knowledge graphs across diverse application domains.

Format and Schedule

The tutorial will be held on **October 16, 2025** as part of the **IJCKG 2025 conference**, and it will be structured to balance conceptual understanding with practical application. It will begin with a slide-based presentation introducing the core concepts of knowledge graph construction and the X3ML framework. This will be followed by a live online demonstration, showcasing the workflow of schema mapping and RDF generation using the framework tools and resources. Finally, participants will engage in guided hands-on exercises to practice defining schema mappings and transforming data collections themselves. The entire session will last one hour, ensuring an engaging and focused learning experience that combines theory, demonstration and active participation within the conference program.

<https://ymark.github.io/X3ML-Tutorial/>

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository for X3ML-Tutorial. The repository is public and has 1 branch and 0 tags. It was last updated by ymark on last week with 44 commits. The file list includes assets, exercises, images, LICENSE.txt, README.md, and index.html. The README section is visible, containing the repository's purpose and learning objectives. The repository description states: "This repository contains resources that accompany the tutorial on knowledge graph construction using the X3ML Framework, presented at IJCKG 2025. It contains exercises that guide users getting familiar with X3ML framework." The learning objectives are: "Through these exercises, participants will learn how to: Design schema mappings using the X3ML language; Use the 3M mapping editor to define correspondences between source data and ontology concepts; Apply mappings with the X3ML Engine to generate RDF aligned with domain ontologies; Explore the transformed RDF data in a user-friendly manner." The repository also shows 0 releases, 0 packages, 39 deployments (including github-pages), and a language usage chart: CSS 42.0%, SCS5 37.0%, JavaScript 13.9%, and HTML 7.1%.

<https://github.com/ymark/X3ML-Tutorial>

Introduction / Motivation

- **Fragmented Reality**
 - Institutions curate diverse collections using different metadata standards, languages and practices
- **The Challenge**
 - This heterogeneity limits data sharing, interoperability, and cross-domain discovery
- **The Goal**
 - Integrate and aggregate metadata into unified, semantically rich knowledge graphs
- **The Benefit**
 - Enable richer research, complex query answering, reuse and share resources

Introduction / Motivation

The role of schema mappings

- Data sources use multiple schemas and formats to describe their contents
 - They describe similar concepts using different structures and terminologies
- To semantically integrate them we need
 - **Schema mappings**
 - Describe the correspondences between the source data elements and the target ontology concepts
 - **Data transformation tools**
 - Apply schema mappings to generate RDF representations of the original data sources aligned with a common target model (i.e. ontology)

Introduction / Motivation

The Data Transformation Workflow

Data Sources

Tutorial Objectives

- Understanding the core definitions and the role of schema mappings in data integration
- Design schema mappings using **X3ML language**
- Use tools (**3M**, **X3ML Engine**) to practice with schema mapping definition and data transformation
- Experiment with different methods for assigning URIs (Uniform Resource Identifier) and labels
- Construction of **interoperable knowledge graphs** from diverse data sources
- Assess and evaluate **data transformation results** for semantic correctness and completeness
- Explore how Large Language Models (LLMs) can **assist** or **automate** parts of the schema mapping process, reducing manual effort and accelerating semantic data integration

X3ML Framework

	X3ML Framework - Specification		
	X3ML Mapping Definition Language	9-16	7'
	X3ML Generator Policy Definition	17-18	3'

X3ML Mapping Definition Language

- X3ML is a declarative, XML based language which describes schema mappings in such a way that they can be collaboratively created and discussed by experts.
- Key Features
 - It provides a declarative way for describing schema mappings
 - Focuses on properly mapping schema resources
 - Decoupled from the URI and values generation process
 - Mappings are described using XML serialization

X3ML Mapping Structure

X3ML Mapping Definition Constructs

X3ML supports **1:N mappings** and uses the following special constructs:

- **Intermediate nodes** used to represent the mapping of a simple source path to a complex target path.
- **Constant expression nodes** used to assign constant attributes to an entity.
- **Conditional statements** within the target node and target relation support checks for existence and equality of values and can be combined into Boolean expressions.
- **“Same as” variable** used to identify a specific node instance for a given input record that is generated once but is used in a number of locations in the mapping.
- **Join operator (==)** used in the source path to denote relational database joins.
- **Info and comment blocks** throughout the mapping specification bridge the gap between human author and machine executor.

X3ML Mapping Definition Language Example

id	Painting title	painter	Creation date	Filename
p-1	Self-Portrait as a Painter	Vincent van Gogh	1888	p1.jpg
p-2	The Starry Night	Vincent van Gogh	1889	p2.jpg
p-3	The Ballet Class	Edgar Degas	1874	p3.jpg

X3ML Mapping Definition Language Example

```

<root>
  <painting>
    <id>p-1</id>
    <painter_id>a-1</painter_id>
    <title>Self-Portrait as a Painter</title>
    <creation_date>1888</creation_date>
    <filename>file1.jpg</filename>
  </painting>
  <painting>
    <id>p-2</id>
    <painter_id>a-1</painter_id>
    <title>The Starry Night</title>
    <creation_date>1889</creation_date>
    <filename>file2.jpg</filename>
  </painting>
  <painting>
    <id>p-3</id>
    <painter_id>a-2</painter_id>
    <title>The Ballet Class</title>
    <creation_date>1889</creation_date>
    <filename>file3.jpg</filename>
  </painting>
</root>

```


X3ML Mapping Definition Language

Structure of mappings

X3ML Mapping Definition Language

Structure of mappings

```
<mapping>
  <domain>
    <source_node>/root/painting</source_node>
    <target_node>
      <entity>
        <type>crm:E22_Human-Made_Object</type>
      </entity>
    </target_node>
  </domain>
  <link>
    <path>
      <source_relation>
        <relation>title</relation>
      </source_relation>
      <target_relation>
        <relationship>crm:P102_has_title</relationship>
      </target_relation>
    </path>
    <range>
      <source_node>title</source_node>
      <target_node>
        <entity>
          <type>crm:E35_Title</type>
        </entity>
      </target_node>
    </range>
  </link>
</mapping>
```


X3ML Generator Policy Definition

- Definition of rules for the generation of URIs and labels (i.e. `rdfs:Label`)

```
<generator name="LocalTerm" prefix="pref">  
  <pattern> {hierarchy}/resource/{term} </pattern>  
</generator>
```

Use common
URI prefix

```
<generator name="SimpleLabel">  
  <pattern> {label} </pattern>  
</generator>
```

Use
parameters
(within { }) and
constants

Generation
using
templates

```
<generator name="LocalTerm-hashed" prefix="pref" shorten="yes">  
  <pattern> {hierarchy}/resource/{term} </pattern>  
</generator>
```

Create hashed
values based
on contents

```
<generator name="LocalTerm-uuid" prefix="pref" uuid="yes">  
  <pattern> {hierarchy}/resource/ </pattern>  
</generator>
```

Declare once,
use multiple
times

Create unique
and random
URIs

X3ML Generator Policy Definition – cont'd

```
<painter>
  <id>a-1</id>
  <name>Vincent Van Gogh</name>
</painter>
<painter>
  <id>a-2</id>
  <name>Edgar Degas</name>
</painter>
```

```
<generator name="LocalTerm" prefix="pref">
  <pattern>{hierarchy}/resource/{term}</pattern>
</generator>
<generator name="SimpleLabel">
  <pattern>{label}</pattern>
</generator>
```

```
<instance_generator name="LocalTerm">
  <arg name="hierarchy" type="constant">persons</arg>
  <arg name="term" type="xpath">painter/id/text()</arg>
</instance_generator>
```

```
<label_generator name="SimpleLabel">
  <arg name="label" type="xpath">painter/name/text()</arg>
  <arg name="language" type="constant">en</arg>
</label_generator>
```

http://.../persons/resource/a-1

http://.../persons/resource/a-2

"Vincent Van Gogh"@en

"Edgar Degas"@en

	X3ML Software		
	3M Editor	20-40	24'
	X3ML Engine	41-42	4'
	RDF Visualizer	43-44	2'

3M Editor

- Enables the creation of mapping definitions (X3ML) between source and target schemata
- Supports guided mappings by analyzing source resources and target schemata
- Provides user space and mapping storage
- Transforms data (in RDF format) using X3ML Engine

3M Mapping : X3ML Toolkit Tutorial Demo Map

Info Matching Table Generators Analysis Transformation Configuration About

▲ TOP ▼ BOTTOM VIEW MODE </> XML

(ALL) SOURCES ↔ (ALL) TARGET PATHS ↔

#	SOURCE	TARGET
1	D <input type="checkbox"/> ./row	<input type="checkbox"/> E31_Document <input type="checkbox"/> E33_Linguistic_Object
1.1	P <input type="checkbox"/> Type	<input type="checkbox"/> P2_has_type
	R <input type="checkbox"/> Type	<input type="checkbox"/> E55_Type
1.2	P <input type="checkbox"/> Creator	<input type="checkbox"/> P94i_was_created_by <input type="checkbox"/> E65_Creation <input type="checkbox"/> [create1]
	R <input type="checkbox"/> Creator	<input type="checkbox"/> P14_carried_out_by <input type="checkbox"/> E39_Actor
1.3	P <input type="checkbox"/> Creator	<input type="checkbox"/> P94i_was_created_by <input type="checkbox"/> E65_Creation <input type="checkbox"/> [create1]
	R <input type="checkbox"/> Creator	<input type="checkbox"/> P14_carried_out_by <input type="checkbox"/> E39_Actor
1.4	P <input type="checkbox"/> Date	<input type="checkbox"/> P94i_was_created_by <input type="checkbox"/> E65_Creation <input type="checkbox"/> [create1]
	R <input type="checkbox"/> Date	<input type="checkbox"/> P4_has_time-span <input type="checkbox"/> E52_Time-Span <input type="checkbox"/> P82_at_some_time_within <input type="checkbox"/> rdf-schema#Literal
1.5	P <input type="checkbox"/> Title	<input type="checkbox"/> P1_is_identified_by
	R <input type="checkbox"/> Title	<input type="checkbox"/> E41_Appellation
1.6	P <input type="checkbox"/> Subtitle	<input type="checkbox"/> P1_is_identified_by
	R <input type="checkbox"/> Subtitle	<input type="checkbox"/> E41_Appellation
1.7	P <input type="checkbox"/> Subject	<input type="checkbox"/> P129_is_about
	R <input type="checkbox"/> Subject	<input type="checkbox"/> E55_Type
1.8	P <input type="checkbox"/> language	<input type="checkbox"/> P72_has_language
	R <input type="checkbox"/> language	<input type="checkbox"/> E56_Language

3M Editor – new version

- Implemented using modern and responsive technologies
- Faster and light-weight (at client side)
- Allows concurrent edits of mappings from different users (a la Google docs)
- In action since 2021

The screenshot shows the 3M Editor interface with a table of mappings. The table has columns for Title, HRID, Author, Status, Date Created, Date Modified, Coverage, and User. Below the table are buttons for OPEN, CLONE, ADD NEW, and IMPORT FROM ZIP, along with pagination and mode controls.

Title	HRID	Author	Status	Date Created	Date Modified	Coverage	User
FIRMS Stock Mappings	278840	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Fri Nov 26 2021 12:02 PM	Wed May 22 2024 03:59 PM		
RTI-NEH	756044	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Mon Nov 29 2021 01:55 PM	Wed Oct 02 2024 12:56 PM	62%	
ARIADNEplus THANADOS mapping OFFICIAL_(cloned)	870295	Maria Theodoridou	In Progress	Thu Dec 02 2021 03:24 PM	Wed Jun 22 2022 04:35 PM		
A KTP to CIDOC -Person	317807	Athina Kitsotaki	In Progress	Mon Dec 13 2021 11:13 AM	Thu May 23 2024 03:57 PM		
A KTP to CIDOC -Organisation	495892	Athina Kitsotaki	In Progress	Wed Dec 15 2021 10:56 AM	Thu May 23 2024 04:19 PM		
Vincent Van Gogh painting	574665	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Wed Feb 09 2022 12:16 PM	Wed Sep 25 2024 03:37 PM		
GRSF-FishingGearsVocabulary	456359	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Thu Mar 03 2022 04:02 PM	Mon Mar 14 2022 03:47 PM	94%	
GRSF-SpeciesVocabulary	452869	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Fri Mar 04 2022 03:15 PM	Wed Jul 02 2025 12:21 PM	48%	
GRSF-WaterAreasVocabulary	478623	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Tue May 17 2022 04:01 PM	Mon Jun 20 2022 02:29 PM	28%	
A KTP to CIDOC -Place	649619	Athina Kitsotaki	In Progress	Thu Jun 09 2022 11:15 AM	Thu May 23 2024 04:43 PM		

The screenshot shows the configuration details for three links in a mapping. Each link configuration includes a Source Relation, Source Node, Target Relation, and Target Entity. The interface also shows a 'Relation' and 'Entity' box for the first link, and a 'Target Entity' box for the second link.

Mapping #1 - Has 3 links (3 links selected)

Link #1 (of mapping #1)
 Source Relation: title
 Source Node: title
 Target Relation: P102_has_title
 Target Entity: E35_Title
 LocalTermURI: {title}/{text0}
 Literal: text: text0

Link #2 (of mapping #1)
 Source Relation: painter_id
 Source Node: painter_id
 Target Relation: P108i_was_produced_by
 Target Entity: E12_Production
 production_event
 UUID
 CompositeLabel: {Creation of painting with title: }{title/text0}
 Target Relation: P14_carried_out_by
 Target Entity: E21_Person
 LocalTermURI: {painter}/{text0}

Link #3 (of mapping #1)
 Source Relation: creation_date
 Target Relation: P108i_was_produced_by
 Target Entity: E12_Production
 production_event

3M Editor

- Key features
 - Guided mappings by analyzing source records and target schemata (i.e. ontologies)
 - Collaborative definition of X3ML mappings
 - Integration with tools (i.e. X3ML Engine for data transformation, RDFVisualization for visualizing transformed data)
 - Smart features to facilitate mapping definition (e.g. copy/clone mappings, disable mappings, etc.)
 - Hybrid definition of mappings (i.e. editing mappings through the UI as well as through their XML serialization)
 - Import and export facilities
 - Enhanced dissemination and collaboration with link-to-share mappings

3M Editor

- Supports the collaborative creation and exchange of (X3ML) mapping definitions
 - Mappings definition
 - Mappings storage
 - Organized in projects
 - Collaborative (many users working on the same project)
 - Supports concurrent schema editing (à la google docs)

The screenshot shows the 3M Editor web interface. At the top is a blue header with a hamburger menu, the '3m' logo, and a user profile icon. Below the header, there's a navigation bar with 'Project - Mappings', two toggle switches for 'Only display those that I own' (off) and 'Only display those I can edit' (on), and a search bar. The main content is a table with columns: Title, HRID, Author, Status, Date Created, and Date Modified. The table lists several mapping projects, mostly in 'In Progress' status, with various authors and creation/modification dates.

Title	HRID	Author	Status	Date Created	Date Modified
A KTP to CIDOC-BookSource	143663	Athina Kritsotaki	In Progress	Fri Oct 21 2022 10:58 AM	Mon Dec 19 2022 09:37 AM
A KTP to CIDOC - NewspaperSource	057576	Athina Kritsotaki	In Progress	Fri Oct 21 2022 01:56 PM	Mon Dec 19 2022 09:37 AM
A KTP to CIDOC-Bibliography	566136	Athina Kritsotaki	In Progress	Mon Oct 24 2022 10:01 AM	Mon Dec 19 2022 09:37 AM
A KTP to CIDOC-DigitalObject	200925	Athina Kritsotaki	In Progress	Mon Oct 24 2022 01:18 PM	Mon Dec 19 2022 09:38 AM
A KTP to CIDOC-SourcePassage	543123	Athina Kritsotaki	In Progress	Tue Oct 25 2022 09:43 AM	Mon Dec 19 2022 09:38 AM
A KTP to CIDOC-SourcePassageCollection	130384	Athina Kritsotaki	In Progress	Tue Oct 25 2022 01:46 PM	Mon Dec 19 2022 09:38 AM
CBDB_person_2	419742	Martin Doerr	In Progress	Sat Jan 28 2023 07:11 PM	Sat Mar 11 2023 10:20 PM
Compact_Conditions	921287	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Thu Mar 09 2023 10:39 AM	Thu Mar 09 2023 10:45 AM
long numbers experimen	617235	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Fri Mar 10 2023 10:01 AM	Fri Mar 10 2023 10:45 AM
Crew_list_Ruoli_di_Equipaggio	875467	Yannis Marketakis	In Progress	Tue Jun 20 2023 03:01 PM	Tue Jun 20 2023 03:50 PM

A new project is created in the form of a workflow (**5 + 1 steps**)

3M Editor – Create a new project

- Step 1: Define a title and a short description for the project

1 Mapping Information — 2 Source Input — 3 Target Schema — 4 URI Generator Policy — 5 Confirmation

Please fill in the following form to create a new "Mapping Project".

Title *

Demo schema mappings

Description

A project with schema mappings created for demonstration purposes

BACK **NEXT**

3M Editor – Create a new project

□ Step 2: Upload (a sample) of the data in their original format

✕

✓ Mapping Information — 2 Source Input — 3 Target Schema — 4 URI Generator Policy — 5 Confirmation

Please add your own file(s) below.

You can add your own "Source Input" files from here, by clicking on the "plus" blue button and then filling in the respective fields.

File #1 ✕

Title *
sample file

Description
some sample data

Version
1.0

raw_data.xml
21 KB

DOWNLOAD

BACK

NEXT

3M Editor – Create a new project

Step 3: Select or upload the target schema/ontology

Mapping Information — Source Input — **3 Target Schema** — 4 URI Generator Policy — 5 Confirmation

Please select one or more Target Schema file(s) from the available list. Additionally, you can further add your own file(s) below.

Select one or more predefined "Target Schema" files from the following list.

<input type="checkbox"/>	CRMsci (1.2.2) The Scientific Observation Model(CRMsci) is a formal ontology intended to be used as a global schema for integrating metadata about scientific observation, measurements and processed data in descriptive and empirical sciences such as biodiversity, geology, geography, archaeology, cultural heritage conservation and others in research IT environments and research data libraries.	
<input type="checkbox"/>	FRBR (2.4) The FRBRoo is a formal ontology intended to capture and represent the underlying semantics of bibliographic information and to facilitate the integration, mediation, and interchange of bibliographic and museum information.	
<input type="checkbox"/>	CIDOC CRM (6.2.1) The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) is a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CIDOC CRM (7.1.1) The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) is a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage	

You can add your own "Target Schema" files from here.

BACK

NEXT

3M Editor – Create a new project

Step 4: Select or upload the URI and values generation policy

Please select one or more Generator Policy file(s) from the available list. Additionally, you can further add your own file(s) below.

Select one or more predefined "Generator Policy" files from the following list.

- Basic Generator Policy Resources (1.0)
Some basic generator policy definitions

You can add your own "Generator Policy" files from here.

BACK

NEXT

3M Editor – Create a new project

□ Step 5: Inspect the project configuration and create the project

×

✓ Mapping Information — ✓ Source Input — ✓ Target Schema — ✓ URI Generator Policy — 5 Confirmation

- Title
Demo schema mappings
- Description
A project with schema mappings created for demonstration purposes
- Source Input
sample file v1.0 (raw_data.xml)
- Target Schema
CIDOC CRM v7.1.1 (CIDOC_CRM_v7.1.1.rdfs)
- Generator Policy
Basic Generator Policy Resources v1.0 (generator-policy.xml)

BACK

FINISH

3M Editor – Create a new project

❑ Extra Step

Participating to this project users ❑ ×

Select any user to allow editing this Mapping Project

Search by name ×

- Nurdan Atalan Çayırmez
Natalan
- Achille Felicetti
akillus
- Kai Salas Rossenbach
kaisalasrossenbach
- David Novák
novak
- Michael English
DEA_livearchive
- Pavlos Fafalios
fafalios
- Marie LAGASSE
Marie

< 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 >

Invite collaborators

Start your mappings project

3M Editor – Defining Schema Mappings

3M Editor – Defining Schema Mappings

- Guided mappings by analyzing source resources and target schemata

<> Domain - Named Graph: *(Optionally add one)*

Source Node

/root/painting

/root

/root/painting

/root/painting/creator

/root/painting/title

/root/painting/creation_date

/root/painting/filename

Target Entity

E2

CIDOC_CRM_v7.1.1

E20_Biological_Object

E21_Person

E22_Human-Made_Object

E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing

E25_Human-Made_Feature

E26_Physical_Feature

E27_Site

3M Editor – Defining Schema Mappings

- Create a **mapping** and a **domain** about painting objects

The screenshot displays the 3M Editor interface. At the top, a header bar shows a checked checkbox, the text "Mapping #1- Has no links (0 links selected)", another checked checkbox, and the text "Named Graph: (Optionally add one)". Below this, a "Domain" configuration panel is visible, titled "Domain - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)". The panel is divided into two sections: "Source Node" and "Target Entity". The "Source Node" section contains a dropdown menu with the value "/root/painting" and a "CONDITION" button below it. The "Target Entity" section contains a dropdown menu with the value "E22_Human-Made_Object" and a close button (X).

crm:E22_Human-made Object

3M Editor – Defining Schema Mappings

- Add an **additional** node to specify the object type

Mapping #1- Has no links (0 links selected) - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)

Domain

Source Node: /root/painting

Target Entity: E22_Human-Made_Object

→ Relation: P2_has_type

Entity: E55_Type

An additional node

3M Editor – Defining Schema Mappings

- Add a **link** for the painting title

Mapping #1 - Has 1 link (1 links selected) - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)

Domain

Source Node: /root/painting Target Entity: E22_Human-Made_Object

→ Relation: P2_has_type
 Entity: E55_Type

Link #1 (of mapping #1)

↓ Source Relation: title ↓ Target Relation: P102_has_title

Source Node: title Target Entity: E35_Title

3M Editor – Defining Schema Mappings

- Add a **link** for the painter

Mapping #1 - Has 2 links (2 links selected) - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)

Domain

Source Node: /root/painting Target Entity: E22_Human-Made_Object

→ Relation: P2_has_type
 Entity: E55_Type

Link #1 (of mapping #1)

Source Relation: title Target Relation: P102_has_title

Source Node: title Target Entity: E35_Title

Link #2 (of mapping #1)

Source Relation: painter_id Target Relation: P108i_was_produced_by

Target Entity: E12_Production
↓ Target Relation: P14_carried_out_by

Source Node: painter_id Target Entity: E21_Person

An intermediate node

3M Editor – Defining Schema Mappings

- Add a **link** for the date of creating the painting

Mapping #1 - Has 3 links (3 links selected) - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)

Domain

Source Node: root/painting Target Entity: E22_Human-Made_Object

→ Relation: P2_has_type
 Entity: E55_Type

Link #1 (of mapping #1)

Source Relation: title Target Relation: P102_has_title

Source Node: title Target Entity: E35_Title

Link #2 (of mapping #1)

Source Relation: painter_id Target Relation: P108i_was_produced_by

Target Entity: E12_Production
Target Relation: P14_carried_out_by

Source Node: painter_id Target Entity: E21_Person

Link #3 (of mapping #1)

Source Relation: creation_date Target Relation: P108i_was_produced_by

Target Entity: E12_Production
Target Relation: P4_has_time-span
Target Entity: E52_Time-Span
Target Relation: P82_at_some_time_within

Source Node: creation_date Target Entity: Literal

Two intermediate nodes

3M Editor – Defining URI & Label Generators

- Define a **URI Generator** for the painting

<> Domain - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)

Source Node
/root/painting

Target Entity
E22_Human-Made_Object Please select target

CONDITION

ADDITIONAL **GENERATOR** VARIABLE

INSTANCE INFO

Generator

INSTANCE LABEL

Please select some definition and then fill in the respective form. Don't forget to save before closing this dialog.

Definitions

- UUID
- Literal
- SimpleLabel
Pattern: {label}
- CompositeLabel
Pattern: {term1} {term2}
- LocalTermURI
Prefix: pref
Pattern: {hierarchy}/{term}
- TypedLiteralGen
- URIorUUID
- UlanUri
Prefix: ulan
Pattern: {ulan_id}

Instance Declaration

LocalTermURI

Argument #1: hierarchy
Select Type
Constant

Value *
painting

Argument #2: term
Select Type
Xpath

Select or add your own XPath *
id/text()

Definition namespace

Prefix: pref
Value *
http://www.example.com/resource/

Will create URIs of the form
http://www.example.com/resource/painting/p1

3M Editor – Defining URI & Label Generators

- Define a **label Generator** for the painting

<> Domain - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)

Source Node
/root/painting

Target Entity
E22_Human-Made_Object Please select target

CONDITION

ADDITIONAL **GENERATOR** VARIABLE

INSTANCE INFO

Will create labels with the title of paintings
e.g. **“Self-Portrait as a Painter”**

Generator

INSTANCE **LABEL**

Please select some definition and then respective form. Don't forget to save before closing this dialog.

Definitions

- Literal
- prefLabel
- SimpleLabel
Pattern: {label}
- CompositeLabel
Pattern: {term1} {term2}
- LocalTermURI
Prefix: pref
Pattern: {hierarchy}/{term}
- TypedLiteralGen
- URlorUUID
- UlanUri
Prefix: ulan
Pattern: {ulan_id}

Label Declaration

SimpleLabel

Argument #1: label
Select Type
Xpath

Select or add your own XPath *

title/text()

Argument #2: language
Select Type
Please select type

Value

SAVE LABEL GENERATOR CLOSE

3M Editor – Defining URI & Label Generators

- Define a **URI Generator** for the painting

The screenshot shows the configuration for a mapping in the 3M Editor. At the top, a header bar indicates 'Mapping #1 - Has 3 links (3 links selected)'. Below this, the 'Domain' is set to 'Source Node:/root/painting'. The 'Target Entity' is 'E22_Human-Made_Object'. Two generators are listed: 'LocalTermURI' and 'SimpleLabel'. The 'LocalTermURI' generator has a green argument '{painting}' and a yellow argument '{id/text0}'. The 'SimpleLabel' generator has a yellow argument '{title/text0}'. Two callout boxes with arrows point to these arguments: 'The URI Generator' points to the green argument, and 'The label Generator' points to the yellow argument.

Mapping #1 - Has 3 links (3 links selected) - Named Graph: (Optionally add one)

Domain

Source Node:/root/painting

Target Entity: E22_Human-Made_Object

LocalTermURI
{painting}/*{id/text0}*

SimpleLabel
{title/text0}

The URI Generator

The label Generator

Green arguments: constant values

Yellow arguments: XPATH expressions (for collecting data from XML input)

3M Editor – Defining URI & Label Generators

```
<painting>
  <id>p-1</id>
  <painter>Van Gogh</painter>
  <title>Self-Portrait as a Painter</title>
  <creation_date>1889</creation_date>
  <filename>file_p-1.jpg</filename>
</painting>
```

```
<painting>
  <id>p-3</id>
  <painter>Degas</painter>
  <title>The Ballet Class</title>
  <creation_date>1874</creation_date>
  <filename>file_p-3.jpg</filename>
</painting>
```

Target Entity: E22_Human-Made_Object

LocalTermURI
{painting}/{id/text()}

http://.../painting/p-1

CompositeLabel
{Painting with title:} {title/text()}

Painting with the title: Self-Portrait as a Painter

Target Entity: E12_Production

production_event

urn:uuid:5178d556-d670-4bf8-b7dc-48e78433edd3

UUID

CompositeLabel
{Creation of painting with title:} {../title/text()}

Creation of the painting with the title: Self-Portrait as a Painter

Target Relation: P14_carried_out_by

Target Entity: E21_Person

LocalTermURI
{painter}/{text()}

http://.../painter/VanGogh

X3ML Engine

- **X3ML Engine** is a tool that realizes the transformation of data resources to a target format with respect to an X3ML Mapping definition language.
- Main principles:
 - Simplicity by design
 - Transparency in terms of expected output
 - Re-use of standards and technologies as much as possible
 - Facilitating the instance matching process

X3ML Engine

- X3ML Engine has been designed by FORTH.
 - The initial development has been carried out by DELVING B.V. under the support and contribution of FORTH (until version 1.3 – March 2015)
 - FORTH took over the full development of X3ML Engine since March 2015.
- 30 Releases in total (Latest one: version 2.2.2 May 2025)
- Available as: API, executable (console-based & GUI), service

Application with UI

CLI tool

```
C:\Repositories\Github\X3ML\target>java -jar x3ml-engine-1.9.4-SNAPSHOT-exejar.jar
usage: x3ml -xml <input records> -x3ml <mapping file> hello
Options
  -a,--assocTable <arg>      export the contents of the association table in XML format
  -f,--format <arg>          Output format. Options:
                             --format application/rdf+xml (default)
                             --format application/n-triples
                             --format application/trig
                             --format text/turtle
                             XML input records.
                             Option A-single file: --input input.xml
                             Option B-multiple files (comma-sep): --input input1.xml,input2.xml,input3.xml
                             Option C-folder: --input # folder_path
                             Option D-URL: --input @input_url
                             Option E-multiple URLs: --input @input_url1,input_url2,input_url3
                             Option F-stdin: --input @
                             merge the contents of the association table with the RDF output
                             The output file name: --output output.rdf
                             The value policy file: --policy policy.xml
                             Reports the progress of the transformations
                             the SKOS taxonomy
                             Option A-single file: --terms skosTerms.nt
                             Option B-URL: --terms @skos_terms_url
                             Create a test UUID generator of the given size.
                             Default is UUID from operating system
                             X3ML mapping definition.
                             Option A-single file: --x3ml mapping.x3ml
                             Option B-multiple files (comma-sep): --x3ml mappings1.x3ml,mappings2.x3ml
                             Option C-URL: --x3ml @mappings_url
                             Option D-stdin: --x3ml @

-i,--input <arg>
-m,--mergeAssocWithRDF
-o,--output <arg>
-p,--policy <arg>
-r,--reportProgress
-t,--terms <arg>
-u,--uuidTestSize <arg>
-x,--x3ml <arg>

Missing required options: i, x
```

JAVA API

```
X3MLEngineFactory.create()
    .withMappings(new File("path/to/mappings.x3ml"))
    .withInputFiles(new File("path_to/input.xml"))
    .withGeneratorPolicy(new File("path/to/generator-policy.xml")
        )
    .withTerminology(new File("path/to/terms.nt"), Lang.NT)
    .withOutput("output.ntriples", X3MLEngineFactory.OutputFormat
        .NTRIPLES)
    .withProgressReporting()
    .execute();
```

RDF Visualizer

RDF Visualizer is a generic browsing mechanism that gives the user a flexible, highly configurable, detailed overview of an RDF dataset/database

The screenshot displays the RDF Visualizer interface for a dataset. On the left, a 'Symbol & color Legend' panel lists categories: Other Entities, Temporal Entities, Actors, Physical Things, Conceptual things, and Places. The main view shows a hierarchical tree of entities for 'ship Andrea [sealit#Ship]'. The tree includes properties like 'sealit#was_constructed_by' (Construction of Andrea), 'P7_took_place_at' (Sestri Ponente), 'sealit#under_name' (Andrea), 'P4_has_time-span' (Construction date 1859), 'P2_has_type' (brigantino), 'P1_is_identified_by' (Andrea), 'sealit#is_registered_by' (Registration of Andrea), 'sealit#has_tonnage' (tonnage of Andrea), 'sealit#has_phase' (Ownership of Andrea), 'sealit#has_owner' (Gaetano Ogno), and 'sealit#voyages' (Voyage of ship Andrea). Red callout boxes highlight: 'Instance label and type (i.e. Class)' pointing to the ship name; 'View URI on hover' pointing to the URI 'urn:uuid:344e313e-766c-4f29-b9ff-fb02ecd52615' shown on hover; 'Expand/collapse information' pointing to a plus sign; and 'Display images and galleries' pointing to an 'Image Gallery' window showing a painting of a three-masted sailing ship.

RDF Visualizer – cont'd

> Expand all mappings

Mapping #1 - Has 3 links (3 links selected)

Mapping #2 - Has 2 links (2 links selected)

RDF Visualizer can be loaded directly from 3M Editor

VALIDATE PATHS

PRODUCE X3ML

PRODUCE RDF

VIEW IN THE RDF VISUALISER

Enter subject

Choose a Template:

Template 1

Mark same instances

Painting with title: Self-Portrait as a Painter [E22_Human-Made_Object]

P2_has_type

P108i_was_produced_by

Creation of painting with title: Self-Portrait as a Painter [E12_Production]

P14_carried_out_by

Vincent Van Gogh [E21_Person]

P1_is_identified_by

P4_has_time-span

P82_at_some_time_within

P102_has_title

Looking to the Future

Introduction

46-47

2'

How LLMs can support?

48

1'

Approaches / Prompts

49-51

2'

First Results

52-53

1'

Issues / Challenges

54

1'

Looking to the Future

Automatic the Definition of X3ML Schema Mappings

- **What?**
 - Automate the transformation of large-scale structured data to RDF Knowledge Graphs
 - Reduce the manual intervention of the schema mapping process
- **Why do we need it?**
 - Considering the tremendous volumes of data and their diversity, speeding up the semantic data integration process is the only way
- **Why it is difficult?**
 - The definition of schema mappings is a manual process
 - It requires domain expertise and mapping experience
 - Ensuring that mappings are accurate is a complex task (i.e. depends on the ontology, the input data, etc.)
- **How?**
 - Focus on automation
 - Investigate how Large Language Models (LLMs) can support the definition of schema mappings
 - Explore different methods and approaches
 - Focus on mappings validation and evaluation

Looking to the Future How LLMs can support?

- Assign LLMs the roles of domain experts, ontology experts, and mapping experts to **automate** the data integration process

Looking to the Future

Why focus on Schema Mappings?

- While other approaches utilize LLMs for transforming data **we focus on generating schema mappings**
 - It is an intermediate step that allows for verification and adjustments before the actual transformation
 - Easier debugging as potential errors (in the data transformation) can be traced by inspecting the mappings that were generated (data transformations using LLMs is a black box)
 - Direct data transformations using LLMs might introduce variability
 - Require to use only a small subset of the actual data
 - More efficient compared to transforming entire data collections using LLMs

Looking to the Future

LLM-Supported Methods and Approaches

- **zero-shot**

- Create a prompt asking the LLM to design X3ML schema mappings using as input
 - the original data
 - the target ontology

> Generate the schema mappings using X3ML mapping language for transforming the given dataset to CIDOC CRM ontology.

Looking to the Future

LLM-Supported Methods and Approaches

- **syntax-aware**

- Create a prompt asking the LLM to design X3ML schema mappings using as input
 - the original data
 - the target ontology
 - x3ml syntax

> Generate the schema mappings using X3ML mapping language for transforming the given dataset to CIDOC CRM ontology. You must generate a valid X3ML file, so you are given a sample X3ML file to understand how it is structured.

Looking to the Future

LLM-Supported Methods and Approaches

- **in-context mapping**

- Create a prompt asking the LLM to design X3ML schema mappings using as input
 - the original data
 - the target ontology
 - relevant x3ml mappings

> Generate the schema mappings using X3ML mapping language for transforming the given dataset to CIDOC CRM ontology. You are given a relevant X3ML mapping file used to describe the schema mappings for similar input like the one provided.

Looking to the Future

Some first results

average accuracy (in-context) \approx **53%**

average accuracy (in-context) of the best performing LLM \approx **65%**

Looking to the Future

Some first results – cont'd

Looking to the Future Issues & Challenges

- The generated X3ML mappings need to be validated
 - Validity of X3ML: is X3ML valid with respect to X3ML Schema?
 - Validity of resources: are resources (e.g. classes) syntactically correct?
 - Validity of resource connectivity: do classes and properties relate (in the adopted ontology)?
 - Validity of semantics: are mappings semantically correct?
- How to evaluate ?
 - Gold standard: real existing mapping projects (from various 3M installations)
 - More than 1500 X3ML mapping projects
- How to deal with the construction of URIs and labels ?

	Conclusion		
	Conclusions and Next Steps	56	1'
	Some Statistics	57	1'
	References and Links	58	1'

Conclusions & Next Steps

Key takeaways

- Integrating heterogeneous data requires **semantic alignment** through schema mappings
- The **X3ML framework** offers a declarative, transparent, and reusable way to transform data into RDF knowledge graphs
- A well-defined schema mapping process ensures the construction of **interoperable and semantically rich knowledge graphs**
- **Tools** that facilitate the definition of schema mappings and promote collaboration of users

Looking Ahead

- X3ML continues to **evolve** toward greater usability
- Large Language Models (LLMs) can assist or **automate** parts of the mapping process
- Integration workflows are moving toward **semi-automated, intelligent pipelines**
- **Community collaboration** promote high-quality schema mappings and strengthen best practices

Some Statistics

Project / Activity	# Mappings	# Links	# RDF Triples
The Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) <i>(so far)</i>	86	315	6.4 million
SemantyFish <i>(so far)</i>	8	210	6.5 million
SeaLit	266	2284	18.5 million
RICONTRANS	116	683	? millions
DLN Sip Archiver	42	164	On demand
SKOS FoodEx2	5	51	2.8 million

References & Links

- Tutorial-related
 - <https://ymark.github.io/X3ML-Tutorial/>
 - <https://github.com/ymark/X3ML-Tutorial> (with exercises)
- X3ML-related
 - <https://github.com/isl/x3ml>
 - <https://demos.isl.ics.forth.gr/3m/Projects>
- Related Publications
 - Marketakis, Y., Lintanff--Castel, M., and Tzitzikas, Y., 2025. **Using LLMs to Automate the Transformation of Any Structured Data to Ontology-based Descriptions** (submitted – under review)
 - Marketakis, Y., Minadakis, N., Kondylakis, H., Konsolaki, K., Samaritakis, G., Theodoridou, M., Flouris, G. and Doerr, M., 2017. **X3ML mapping framework for information integration in cultural heritage and beyond. International Journal on Digital Libraries**, 18(4), pp.301-319.
 - Minadakis, N., Marketakis, Y., Kondylakis, H., Flouris, G., Theodoridou, M., de Jong, G. and Doerr, M., 2015, September. **X3ML Framework: An Effective Suite for Supporting Data Mappings**. In EMF-CRM@TPDL (pp. 1-12).

From Chaos to Knowledge Graphs – Mission Accomplished! 🚀

Thanks for mapping with us!

Any Questions ?

Scan for more

